

ANALYSIS OF PARENTS' KNOWLEDGE REGARDING EARLY MARRIAGE IN KUTAI KARTANEGARA DISTRICT

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Abstract

According to the United National Children's Fund (UNICEF), the incidence of early marriage has shifted to urban areas, this is marked by an increase in cases of early marriage in urban areas from 2% in 2015 to 37% in 2022. This means that cases of early marriage can occur anywhere and at any time, so parents and the environment must help children marry at the right age. Cases of early marriage are not new in Indonesia. Early marriage is a social problem that occurs among teenagers. The most victims of early marriage are teenage girls. In general, cases of early marriage occur more often in rural areas than urban areas, and often occur in poor families, with low education and school dropouts. The aim of this research is to determine the relationship between parental knowledge and early marriage. This type of quantitative research with a cross-sectional analytical descriptive research design. The population in this research were all young women in Bukit Raya Village, totaling 80 respondents. The sample was 30 respondents. Non-probability sampling method with purposive sampling technique. Data collection techniques use interviews. The data analysis technique uses univariate analysis with frequency distribution. The results of chi-square analysis using SPSS 25 software at an error level of 5%, obtained a p-value of 0.003 (p-value < 0.005). From these results, it can be said that there is a relationship between the level of parental knowledge and approval for early marriage.

Keywords: Early Marriage, Knowledge, Parents, Teenagers

1. INTRODUCTION

According to the United National Children Fund (UNICEF), the incidence of early marriage has shifted to urban areas, this is marked by an increase in cases of early marriage in urban areas from 2% in 2015 to 37% in 2022 (1). This means that cases of early marriage can occur anywhere and at any time, so parents and the environment must help children marry at the right age. Cases of early marriage are not new in Indonesia. Early marriage is a social problem that occurs among teenagers (1).

Based on data from the East Kalimantan Provincial Government in 2020, data was obtained that in 2019 there were 845 cases of early marriage, while up to the first semester of 2020 it had fallen to 418 cases consisting of 89 men and 329 women, which is stated to have decreased in 2020 when compared to the previous year (2). Based on data from the Tenggara Seberang Class II Religious Court in 2020, data was found on the increase in early marriage among teenagers, in 2019 there were 28, and in 2020 there were 72 and 60% of the causes were pregnancies outside of marriage (2).

Parents' knowledge about the age of marriage plays an important role in breaking the chain of cases of early marriage. For this reason, parents must understand what is a good age for marriage. According to the 2014 Marriage Law, the National Population and Family Planning Agency, which is still used today, sets the appropriate age for marriage for men at 25 years and women at 21 years. Lack of parental understanding about the appropriate age for marriage has led to many cases of early marriage. This occurs not only in Indonesia, but several studies report that this case also occurs in other countries. A preliminary study was carried out in Bukit Raya

Village on January 20 2022, in 2021 the results showed that there were 80 young women who married at an early age from 19 Neighborhood Units (2).

Meanwhile, based on data in January 2022, there were 9 young women who married at an early age. From the background above, the author is interested in research into the impact of early marriage on young women who have dropped out of school. The author found that there are many problems that occur in the Bukit Raya Village area, so the author feels that this should be used as research in the hope that it can be used as a reference for efforts to prevent early marriage in teenage girl.

2. METHODOLOGY

The type of research used is quantitative research with a cross-sectional descriptive research design. According to Budiarto (2021), descriptive research with a cross-sectional approach was carried out purely to provide descriptions without conducting in-depth analysis. Cross-sectional is a study in which the independent variables/causal factors/risk factors and dependent variables/result factors/effect factors are collected at the same time. Cross-sectional research is the collection of information from 2 variables carried out simultaneously or simultaneously at one time for each subject and only observed once (Adiputra et al., 2021).

This research was carried out in Bukit Raya Village in January – August 2023. The population used in the research was all 80 young women attending junior high school in Bukit Raya Village. The results of this study show the characteristics of the research sample. The number of teenagers who marry early is 30 people. The technique used to determine the sample in this research is purposive sampling where the researcher has personally selected the sample that will be respondents who meet the researcher's inclusion criteria. The sample that will be studied by researchers is 30 young women. The processing of primary data obtained includes data entry, data processing and statistical data analysis carried out by computerization, namely by using the SPSS program to conduct data analysis with descriptive analysis and inferential analysis, namely Normality Test, Homogeneity Test, Chi Square Test.

3. RESULTS

The results of this study show the characteristics of the research sample. The number of teenagers who marry early is 30 people.

Table 1. Respondent Characteristics

Characteristics	n	%
Age		
16 years	3	10.0
17 years	6	20.0
18 years	2	6,7
19 years old	19	63.3
Religion		
Islam	26	86.7
Christian	4	13.3
Ethnic group		
Java	4	13.3
Buginese	17	56.7
Kutai	9	30.0
Education		
Didn't finish middle school	30	100.0
Work		
Housewife	21	70.0
Self-employed	9	30.0
Current Marital Status		

Marry		27	90.0
Widow		3	10.0
Causative factor Knowledge			
	(Yes)	8	26.7
	(No)	22	73.3
Reasons for Marriage			
	Marriage by Accident	9	30.0
	Economy	21	70.0
Impact of Early Marriage			
Health			
	Age <19 years have <3 children	18	60.0
	Age 16 years 3/more children	7	23.3
	Age 17 years 3/more children	5	16.6
Social			
	Ostracized by Society	26	86.6
	Divorce	3	10.0
	Domestic Violence	1	3.3
Economy			
	Part time work	16	53.3
	Doesn't Work	14	46.7

Source: Primary Data, 2023.

As many as (10%) of respondents at the age of 16 years already had 3/more than 7 children, while almost half (20%) of respondents at the age of 17 years already had 3/more than 5 children. The social impact of early marriage (10%) of respondents experienced divorce as many as 3 people, while a small percentage (3.3%) of respondents experienced domestic violence in the household as many as 1 person. The economic impact of early marriage shows that 14 respondents (46.7%) of respondents do not work. The economic impact of early marriage shows that all 14 mothers (100.0%) of respondents do not work.

Table 2. Value of Parents' Knowledge regarding Early Marriage

Variable	N	Min	Max	Mean	Early Marriage
Value of Parent's Knowledge	30	17.39	95.65	61.44	18.82

Source: Primary Data, 2023.

Table 2 shows the value of parents' level of knowledge regarding early marriage. From the knowledge level data of 30 respondents, the minimum value was 17.39, the maximum value was 95.65, the average was 61.44, and the standard deviation was 18.82.

Table 3. Level of Parental Knowledge regarding Early Marriage

Knowledge level	Number	Percentage (%)
Not enough	15	50%
Enough	9	30%
Good	6	20%
Amount	30	100%

Source: Primary Data, 2023

Table 3 shows the level of knowledge of parents regarding early marriage. From the data on the knowledge level of 30 respondents, 15 respondents (50%) had a poor level of knowledge, 9 respondents (30%) had a sufficient level of knowledge, and 6 respondents (20%) had a good level of knowledge.

Table 4. Statistical Results of Chi-Square Analysis of Parents' Level of Knowledge Regarding Early Marriage

		Early Marriage				P-Value
		Yes		No		
		n	%	n	%	
Knowledge Level	Not Enough	0	0%	15	100%	0.003
	Enough	3	33.3%	6	66.6%	
	Good	4	66.6%	2	33.3%	
Total		7	23.3%	23	76.6%	

Source: Primary Data, 2023.

Table 4 shows the statistical results of chi-square analysis of parents' level of knowledge regarding early marriage. For the level of insufficient knowledge, 15 respondents (100%) did not agree with early marriage. For a sufficient level of knowledge, 6 respondents (66.6%) did not agree with early marriage and 3 respondents (33.3%) agreed with early marriage. For a good level of knowledge, 4 respondents (66.6%) agreed to early marriage and 2 respondents (33.3%) did not agree to early marriage.

Based on the results of chi-square analysis using SPSS 25 software at an error level of 5%, the p-value was 0.003 (p-value <0.005). From these results, it can be said that H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted, which means, there is a relationship between the level of parental knowledge and approval of early marriage.

Based on the data above, it can be seen that the majority (63.3%) of the respondents had 19 high school graduates and almost half (36.7%) had 11 junior high school graduates. It can also be seen from the profile of the development level of bukit raya village where the general education pass results were: kindergarten (2,306 people); elementary school (1,153 people); junior high school (720 people); sma/smu (1,200 people); d1/d3 (41 people); bachelor (127 people); postgraduate (3 people). It can be seen that the education level of the population is still low, which is one of the factors causing early marriage in the village. The results of chi-square analysis using spss 25 software at an error level of 5%, obtained a p-value of 0.003 (p-value <0.005). From these results, there is a relationship between the level of parental knowledge and approval for early marriage. This is in line with nazli halawani pohan's research in 2016 where based on the results of the chi square test it was seen that there was a relationship between education and early marriage in young women with a value of p=0.0005 which means smaller than $\alpha=0.05$, as well as a value of odd ratio (or) of 5.78 with primary education has a 5.78 times risk of early marriage compared to young women with secondary education (3).

Of course, this low education can affect the knowledge of young women. Low education will make it difficult for a person to understand the latest information they obtain, especially information related to their reproductive health. Their lack of knowledge regarding reproductive health, especially the impact of early marriage, will influence their decision to marry early. The inability of young women to continue formal education to a higher level is due to economic problems. Therefore, it is hoped that young women who cannot continue their formal education to a higher level (3).

A low level of education or not continuing education to a further level in this case can encourage someone to enter into early marriage. Apart from that, the level of family education can also influence the occurrence of young marriages. Young marriage is also influenced by the level of education of society as a whole. Some communities with low levels of education tend to marry off their children at a young age. Based on research conducted in gejugjati and lekok districts, pasuruan regency, 35% of couples who married underage were influenced by educational factors. It can be concluded that education is one of the factors that causes early marriage, namely adolescent education and parental education (4).

In this case, teenagers who marry early marry because they have dropped out of school, so because they have no work and are busy, this causes them to choose to marry. Apart from that, several teenagers also said that their parents did not provide enough insight into school. This happens a lot, especially if the parents have low education and poor economic conditions. The alternative of marriage is an option for unemployed children who do not work and do not go to school. So the low level of education or knowledge of parents, children and society influences their mindset in understanding and comprehending the meaning of the purpose of marriage (4).

The researcher's assumptions based on the results of interviews with several sources, it can be concluded that the factors of early marriage that occur in bukit raya village include parental factors. Proposed. Moreover, the young man who proposed to her was from among the rich. Parents hope that by marrying their children they can improve their social status in society. The role of parents in preventing early marriage is very necessary because early marriages carried out by children cannot be separated from the level of education of their parents. Most children who marry at an early age are due to the low level of education of their parents, whereas the high level of parental education will influence the child's education level.

This will be able to prevent early age marriages. Parents will not easily match their children because parents will definitely have considerations before agreeing to the marriage. Don't just because they want to increase their social status in society, parents will easily give their children to be married off. All (100%) of these teenagers do not know the impact of early marriage on their health and future. They said they were only following directions from their parents and there were also some who were dating and became pregnant out of wedlock. Knowledge about good reproduction will give more consideration to marriage, including the age of marriage, because they are more aware of the impact of early marriage on reproductive health (5). This can be seen from the large number of respondents who do not know what early marriage is and what the actual impact of marrying at an early age is. The reason for the lack of knowledge among young women is because the majority of young women have secondary education (sma) and their age is still under 20 years (adolescent age), causing their mindset to be immature and mature in receiving the information provided and also making decisions. Apart from that, the role of health workers is still lacking in health promotion activities, especially regarding the issue of early marriage. Health promotion activities in schools and the community are still lacking, resulting in less knowledge among teenagers in particular and society in general, especially about the impact of early marriage (3).

4. CONCLUSIONS

There is a relationship between the level of parental knowledge and approval of early marriage. Factors that influence early marriage are marriage due to a case and economy.

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